

Research Article

Illocutionary Hate Speech Act at Comment Section of YouTube Account Atta Halilintar (Analysis of Forensic Linguistics)

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Received: February 18, 2023

Accepted: March 05, 2023

Published: March 12, 2023

Abstract: Illocutionary hate speech act often seems at social media. One of them is seemed at comment section on YouTube account. It is written either by children, teenager, or adult. To minimize the crimes at social media, the government applies law ITE (Electronic Information and Transactions). The research is aimed to analyze the kind of illocutionary hate speech act that was seemed at comment section on YouTube account belongs to Atta Halilintar, posted at 18th and 20th May 2021. The method of this research used descriptive qualitative. The data sources used are primary and secondary. The primary data is from comment section YouTube account belongs to Atta Halilintar. While secondary, it is as support from primary data that taken by documentation using book as media, journal, and previous study. The result of this research is showed that there are five assertive speech acts, two expressive speech acts, and one directive and commissive speech acts. Those all are about hate speech acts. They have implicit meaning about hating and mocking. It is caused of hate feeling. Then, netizens try to show their existence in order that everyone could know them in social media. The society forget about the social norms that works in society. It is included how to use polite language in order that it could not harm a people's privacy. Then, they break ITE law on Pasal 27 Ayat 3.

Keywords: Linguistics, Forensics, Speech, Illocutionary, Hate Speech.

Introduction

Language is a tool used to communicate with people. Usually, people could also use the other tools to communicate, but language seems as the best communication tool among the others. In every communication, people could tell some information each other. It is a thought, argument, aim, feel, and emotion. It told immediately in order that language has some impacts for people's life. According to Ullmann (2011: 13), an abstract language could not be reached immediately by the observer without using a media like a dictionary and grammar as guidebook. Even though, the fact is language always appears as individual act of speech. Therefore, every analysis of language structure has to be begun from the speech analysis itself, and it appears a spoken language.

Exactly, the speech is one of phenomenon in the largest problem. It is known with pragmatic. Pragmatic is used to be defined as "the analysis of the correlation between sign and interpretation". Sign is speech unit; it is either in a sentence or more. It could represent a certain meaning. In pragmatic, it must be determined based on the hearing result from the observer (Adriana, 2018: 21). Yuliana (2013: 03) said that pragmatic is one of branch of grammar related to speech act. According to Yule, pragmatic is a study about the correlation between linguistic and grammar user. Levison also explained that pragmatic is the analysis of the correlation between language and its context as a basic of a report about language understanding. In the other word, the analysis of language user's ability could correlate and harmonize the sentences and their context appropriately. The context of

speech act has an important role. The context in the different situation could influence the aim and goal from speech act delivered by speech actor.

Kridalaksana said on Putrayasa's book (2014: 85) that speech act is speech sentence to tell something in order that the aims and speech could be able to be understood by listener. Speech act is a speech made as a part of social interaction. Speech act is individual psychological symptoms. It is determined by speaker language skill to face a certain situation. Speech act is emphasized as a meaning, while the incident is emphasized as a purpose of its incident itself. Hutajulu dan Herman (2019: 30) gave the same opinion about speech act, that speech act is a speech used to explain how the speaker uses the language to reach an intended action and how the listener make a conclusion about the intended meaning that was told.

Actually, when someone is using a language, so, basically, they are doing an action. When the speech said as an action, so it could not be separated from the value because the speech is designed to reach the certain purpose by the speaker. Spoken speech might be able to have a law impact when the speech could be felt by the listener, for example as the speech act could be able to hurt the others or the listener (Bachari dalam Thamrin, 2019: 425). Searle said in his book, *Speech Acts: An Essay in The Philosophy of Language* as quoted in Adriana (2018: 28), that there are three of speech act that could be realized by the speaker. *First*, locutionary act is speech act used to tell something. It called as the act of saying something. *Second*, illocutionary act is what is the purpose of the speaker when telling something. It could be promising, apologizing, threaten, predicting, reigning, asking, and others. Illocutionary act is called as the act of doing something. *Third*, perlocutionary act is a speech act that the speech purposed on influencing the listener, for example, embarrasses, intimidate, persuade, and others. It is called as the act of affecting someone. The three speech acts are managed by rules or norms of language use in the conversation between two people, for example, lecture situations, introductory situations, religious ceremony situations, and so on.

All kinds of speech acts could be found in people communication in daily life. It is spoken or written, as like parents forbid their children to do something, the government gives orders to the people, and also netizen who like or dislike to the actress' content. According to Wijana dan Rohmadi (2009) on Rosyidi, et al. (2019: 736), sometimes, the speech act was spoken by the speaker not also has one meaning. Even though, it has a certain purpose from the speaker to the listener. The purpose of speaker to the listener is called as illocutionary act. Then, Stambo and Ramadhan (2019: 251) said that illocutionary act could be called as the most important speech act in analyzing and understanding the speech act itself. In analyzing the central illocutionary speech act has divided into five points. They are as follow:

- a) Directive speech act, is a speech act that is done by the speaker in order that the listener do what the speaker purposed. It covers the speech act of ordering, inviting, asking, pleading, suggesting, urging and advising.
- b) Expressive speech act, is a speech act that is done and aimed to assess and evaluate something in the speech spoken by the speaker. It covers praise, criticize, thank, complain, apologize, and congratulate.
- c) Representative or assertive speech acts are speech acts that bind the speaker to the truth of the proposition expressed in his speech. For example, stating, informing, expressing opinions, boasting, reporting, showing, and mentioning.
- d) Commissive speech acts are speech acts that bind the speaker to carry out the things mentioned in the speech. For example, promise, swear, offer, and threaten.
- e) Declaration speech acts are speech acts performed with the intention of creating new circumstances. For example, decide, cancel, prohibit, and allow.

The influence of electronic and communication technology that has been increase and developed, the communication is not also be done directly, but it has taken advantages from technological developments. The advantages of technology in communication could be seen from the presence of

social media. Social media gives the convenience for society in interaction in order that there are many people that have been helped by it and operated it. It is a positive impact of the presence of social media. One of social media that most interested by society is a YouTube. The user might upload, watch, share video, and they also could write some comments about the video watched in the commentary section freely. By the development, it could give a significance impact to the society in communication. Dealing with this case, Suryani, et al. (2021: 109) said that the message told by social media would have some impacts. It could be a hate comment from the society. The impact has been varied. Someone could give a good or hurt comment. Everyone who has a social media account could tell their thought or feeling. Even though, there are many social media users that ignore the risk, in order that it could hurt the other with insults, hate speech, and defamation.

Nowadays, the role of language in the spotlight in the legal field. It is seemed from how many cases of defamation, hate speech, and insults that have been delivered on media social, one of them is in the comment column on Atta Halilintar's YouTube account. The linguists use a linguistics to help in solving the legal case. Linguistics used is forensic linguistic. Forensic linguistics is an applied linguistics that involves the relationship between language, crime, and law. The law referred to includes the administration of law, judicial matters, legislation, and other legal processes aimed at seeking legal remedies. Forensic linguistics is used as the application of linguistics that underlies a particular science to the practice of other sciences. Forensic linguistics applies linguistic theories in a linguistic event involved in the legal process, both in the form of legal products, interactions in the judicial process, and in interactions between individuals that result in certain legal impacts. In this case, Coulthard and Johnson (2010) said that the theory of linguistics applied cover the theory of linguistic theory, conversation, discourse analysis, cognitive linguistics, speech acts, theories and techniques of descriptive linguistics, such as phonetics and phonology, lexis, syntax, semantics, pragmatics, discourse, and text analysis. Olsson (2008: 3) said that forensic linguistics is interdisciplinary science among the language, crime, and law. While McMenamin (dalam Muhammad, 2020: 91) said that forensic linguistic is applied linguistic that tries to analyze scientifically about evidence of linguistics from a crime. It is purposed for law enforcement. In the other word, forensic linguistic is application of principle and method in linguistic analysis in the law case and its enforcement.

Therefore, to minimize the crime in social media, the government through the Ministry of Communication and Information applies the ITE Law (Electronic Information and Transactions). They are; Article 27 Paragraph 3 of the ITE Law states that it prohibits anyone from intentionally and without rights distributing and/or transmitting and, or making accessible Electronic Information and, or Electronic Documents containing insults and/or defamation (Menkominfo, 2019). With the enactment of the ITE Law, everyone who speaks on social media must maintain good speech when making conversations or writings to be shown to the public (Thamrin, *et al.*, 2019: 423). If every social media user understands the law, so there will not be a violation.

Method

This article titled Illocutionary hate speech act at comment section of YouTube account Atta Halilintar (analysis of forensic linguistics). It uses descriptive qualitative method. Bogdan and Taylor in Moleong (2011: 04), defines that qualitative method is as research procedure that it results a descriptive data, especially a written data or spoken from the participant that have been observed from social and linguistic phenomenon. This research purposed to describe the illocutionary speech act, especially hurt illocutionary speech act at comment section of YouTube account Atta Halilintar, published on 18th and 20th May 2021. There are two data sources used, primary and secondary. Primary data is a grand data. It is from the comment section of YouTube account Atta Halilintar. While secondary data is as a supporting data for primary data. It comes from the documentation through book as media and previous similar researcher. This research is through the identification and classification based on the pragmatic theory about the speech act. The method used in collecting the data is listening method and some of the techniques. It uses method of reading carefully,

understanding every content by reading the whole notes, listening to every reading while noting some speech indicated there will be hurt illocutionary speech act. It is included into assertive, directive, expressive, commissive, or declarative; and it might have potential to break UU ITE law and KUHP about insult and hurt speech at comment section of YouTube account Atta Halilintar. It is conducted by using qualitative method based on the speech act.

Result and Discussions

Data have been collected based on the result of research about the speech act spoken by netizen at comment section of YouTube account Atta Halilintar, published on 18th and 20th May 2021, that was indicated that there is a sentence about hurt illocutionary speech act. It might have potential to break UU ITE law Pasal 27 Ayat 3 UU ITE; states that it prohibits anyone from intentionally and without rights distributing and or transmitting and, or making accessible Electronic Information and, or Electronic Documents containing insults and or defamation (Menkominfo, 2019). The data found are as follow;

1) Representative or Assertive Speech Acts

Representative or assertive speech acts are speech acts that bind the speaker to the truth of the proposition expressed in his speech. For example, stating, suggesting, boasting, complaining, and daiming.

Data 1

Rafatar anak terkaya se indoo eisssttt salah yang bener adalah anak atta embrio aja udah hasilin adsen pftt. (Rafatar is the richest children around Indonesia eisssttt wrong. The most right is Atta's child, it is still be embryo, it can have AdSense pftt.)

The speech is written on data 1 by netizen named Eri Yunaldi. It is written on 6th June 2021, it is purposed to tell it. It is told to insult the embryo (the result of fertilization of the egg cell at an early stage which later becomes a fetus, which is between one week to eight weeks) that is in Aurel Hermansyah's worm, Atta Halilintar's wife who has been miscarriage. Netizen said that Rafatar, Raffi Ahmad and Nagita Slavina's child is not the richest child in Indonesia, but Atta and Aurel's embryo that has not been born to the world, has been able to make money. It is because Atta create a content video about it, then it is uploaded into their YouTube account. The similar comment has been written by the other netizen, as like this;

-Ismail Saleh_1EA04: gua cemburu sama anaknya padahal masih zigot udah bisa memberikan penghasilan kepada orang tuanya gua mamsih bebean kearg. (I am jealous to his child. It is still be a zygote, but it has been able to give income to his parents. Gua mamsih bebean kearg)

Data 2

Tuhan menutup aibmu rapat rapat, namun kamu membuka aibmu sesuka hatimu, terserah deh wkwk. (God has been closed your shame closely, but you open it as like as you want, it is up to you wkwk).

The speech is written on data 2 by netizen named Fitri Oppo. It is written on 11th June 2021, it is aimed for daiming. She written about the fact related to the god who has been closed people's shame. Unfortunately, Atta create a video about his wife's miscarriage, then upload it into his private YouTube account, in order that it could become public consumption. The shame is not closed anymore, but it opened as like as they want. The similar comment has been written by the other netizen, as like this;

-Samuel Tule: Tuhan menutup aibmu, namun kamu mengumbar aibmu. (God has been closed your shame, but you have been opened it)

Data 3

Baru 5 minggu udah membantu ekonomi keluarga: v (it is just five months. It could help family economy: v).

The speech is written on data 2 by netizen named Hendra Kurniawan. It is written on 6th June 2021, it is aimed for boasting. It is because of society freedom in telling opinion. Netizen could write some nonsense statement without thinking before, it might hurt or not. They insult Atta's wife that the pregnant is just five months has been able to help family economy. The speech written because they dislike about Atta's content video, because he tells everything about his wife's story which she is miscarriage. Netizen think that Atta takes advantage from the situation to make money. Even though Atta's intention is nothing, but to share his experiences to be used as lessons. The similar comment has been written by the other netizen, as like this;

-Denis Andrean: *Blm lahir aja udh jadi tulang punggung: v (it has not been born, but it has been the backbone: v)*

-Luwak white Coffe: *Bru lahir langsung jadi tulang punggung (it has just been born, it has been would be the backbone)*

-mamanVi OFFICIAL: *Anaknya belum lahir udah jadi tulang punggung: D: D: D. (the child has not been born, but it has been the backbone: D: D: D.)*

Data 4

Gppa lah keguguran yg penting dapat money, time is money (it is okay to miscarriage. The important thing is to get money. Time is money)

The speech is written on data 4 by netizen named Syaidil fahmi. It is written on 6th June 2021, it is aimed for boasting. Netizen could write a nonsense statement. He said that it is okay to miscarriage. The important this is to get money. In order that, it represents that money is everything for Atta Halilintar, and miscarriage is not the important thing to be sad, because it has been changed with money from the video uploaded. The similar comment has been written by the other netizen, as like this;

-Dzakwan: *Bersedih tidak perlu, money number one: D: p. (it is not to be sad. Money is number one: D: p.)*

Data 5

Miris yah ngejual privasi semua demi konten dan cuan cuan cuan (It's sad to sell all privacy for the sake of content and cuan cuan cuan)

The speech is written on data 5 by netizen named Sry Anti. It is written on 30th May 2021, it is aimed for telling. Hurt speech is a linguistic phenomenon which is contrary to the concept of language politeness as an indicator of linguistic intelligence and communication ethics. The speech written by netizen to tell the statement that it is so sad to Atta who has sell his privacy for content and money. As if money is everything in order that he need not to be closed. Everything in his family is content, then it is uploaded into his YouTube account. The similar comment has been written by the other netizen, as like this;

-Naufal aqilah: *Emng adsanse yang penting buat lu bang, privasi atau apapun itu no sekian gokil semangat cari cuan bos (AdSense is the most important for you, bang. No place for your privacy. It is crazy. Keep spirit to make money, bos)*

-GUMILANG Pamungkas: *Privacy tidak perlu. Adsense lah nomer satu (no need to privacy. AdSense is number one.)*

-GenoszXgaming: *Apakah dikeluarga ini atau dichenel ini tidak ada privasi sama sekali semuanya aja dipublish. (any privacy in this family or this channel?)*

-Lexry: *Cuan Ngilir Lurr Xixixi (Cuan is coming, Lurr Xixixi)*

-Im not hooman: *Anak Keguguran Ambil hikmahnya X Ambil cuannya √ (child is miscarriage X take the cuan √)*

-Agas Phanee: *SELAMAT DATANG ADSANSE ☺ (Welcome to AdSense ☺)*

2) Expressive Speech Act

Expressive speech act, is a speech act that has function to tell point a psychological attitude from the speaker to a result situation from observation and evaluation. The example of this speech act is thanking, congratulating, pardoning, blamming, hate, praising, and condoling.

Data 1

Kenapa comment lebih berkualitas dari video. (why does the comment have more quality that the video?)

The speech is written on data 1 by netizen named Affan ksoes. It is written on 10th June 2021, it is purposed to praise. Even though, the praise is aimed to the comment, not to Atta's video uploaded. He thinks that the comment has more quality that the video. Mostly, every comment in the video is hate comment. It represents how the netizen hate and criticize about Atta's content video which telling about his wife's miscarriage, Aurel Hermansyah. Even though, there is still some netizen give some support for them. The similar comment has been written by the other netizen, as like this;

-Sano Manjiro: *Datang, Pause video, Baca komen, Yg sama sini ngumpul (coming, pause the video, read the comment, who the same with me? Come here)*

-Agendosa_: *Baru lihat 5 detik stop video langsung lihat komen nya (it is just five second playing, I pause the video, then watch the comment)*

-Tri raudiatu Zahra: *Saya dtng karna Cuma mo baca komen: D. (I am coming just for reading the comment, then thumbs up: D)*

-JAAX: *Klik-dislike-lihat komen-pergi~\ (click-dislike-watch the comment-gone~\)*

-Adi Saputra: *yang kesini Cuma mau baca komentar kasih jempolnya (who is coming here just for reading the comment? Thumbs up)*

-Rarariri Ramadani: *Klik video langsung pause langsung buka komentar(click the video, pause, read the comment directly)*

-Arsyad Al-Fatih: *Paus aja lah. Mnding baca2 koment. Lebih asik.. wkwk (pause it. I am more interested to read the comment. It is very enjoyable.)*

Data 2

GOBLO. PRIVASI KOK DIUMBAR. Atau jangan jangan ini hanya setingan (FU*K. WHY ARE YOU TELLING YOUR PRIVACY? Perhaps, this is in settings.*

The speech is written on data 2 by netizen named "iam human". It is written on 25th May 2021, it is purposed to hate. The hate speech written by netizen is very clear. He said that "Atta GOBLO*" (Atta is stupid). Even though the word is written without the right word, but every netizen who read this could be able to read and understand it. It is *goblok* (very stupid). The word is written by capital letter. It means that he told it loudly. He thinks that Atta is very stupid because he has told his privacy through the video that he has uploaded into his YouTube account. It is aimed to make money. Netizen also thinks that when Aurel is miscarriage is in settings. The similar comment has been written by the other netizen, as like this;

-Aelx Sandro: *Makin kesini makin allay anzim (the more here, the more lazy anzim)*

The speech judge that the content created by Atta Halilintar does not have quality more and more. Netizen also written a hat comment; *anzim*. It has negative meaning. It same as *anjing* (dog), even though it is not written as a clear word.

3) Directive Speech Act

Directive speech act, is a speech act that is purposed by the speaker to influence, so that the listener do what speaker purposed. For example, ordering, commanding, requesting, advising, and recommending.

Data 1

Ini bagus nih di jadiin inspirasi judul film Indosiar "Anaku Sumber Adsansku" (this is so good. It could be inspiration to be the title of Indosiar cinema; "My child is my AdSense")

The speech is written on data 1 by netizen named EGHDIY. It is written on 6th June 2021, it is aimed to recommend. Recommendation written by netizen is not about the quality of a good or nice video. He thinks that the video has a unique content, in order that he invites the other to watch the video. Unfortunately, he recommended to create a cinema titled "My child is my AdSense". Actually, it is right that a child is a source of fortune for their parents. In this case, the child of Atta Halilintar and Aurel Hermansyah has not been born. It is just five weeks, then she was miscarriage. Then, Atta and Aurel use this situation to be a content in mourning. It is to make money, netizen thought.

4) Commissive Speech Act

Commissive speech act is a speech act that has function to tell promise or order. The example of this speech act is promising, vowing, threatening, and offering.

Data 1

Next jangan terlalu diumbar ya kak takutnya kena 'ain. 'Ain itu bahaya ditutup rapat rapat aja. (next, do not show about it too much. It is afraid to 'ain. 'ain is dangerous. It is good to close it closely.)

The speech is written on data 1 by netizen named Diyanti 377. It is written on 23rd May 2021, it is aimed to threaten. Netizen judges that Atta Halilintar over tells about his life on social media.

It could make Atta Halilintar and his family suffering 'ain. 'Ain is a heart disease that make someone inflict and other people around them. People around them could be very jealous to them. Aurel is the first pregnant time. Javanese think that she should not tell about it on social media, before the pregnant is coming to be stronger. The similar comment has been written by the other netizen, as like this;

-Eka dwi Aryani: *Kata orang Jawa dulu mah..kalo pas hamil muda jangan diberitakan sebelumnya kehamilan nya bener 2 kuat...(the old Javanese said that a young pregnant should not tell it to everyone before it has been stronger.)*

-Entin Sri haeti: *Bener disamping itupun baiknya jangan terlalu di umbar 2 karna 'ain itu nyata (it is right. Beside that, it is good to not show it too much, because 'ain is real)*

-Rahmat Hidayat: *Pelajaran yg didapat: "jangan terlalu di umbar 2/riak"(do not show it too much/riyak)*

-Anisa Fitri: *Penyakit ain itu bekas pamer aj kerjanya. ('ain disease is showing something too much)*

-Marwah At-thahirah: *klo masih hamil muda jgn di kasi tau di public dulu tunggu 2 bulanan atau 4 bulanan, bisa jadi kena penyakit ain', karna ad yg muji tpi g menyebut allah di dlm nya..(when you*

are a younger pregnant, you should not show anyone or public. You should wait it for about two for months. It could be 'ain disease. Because there will be someone who praise you without saying name of Allah.)

Conclusion

In this research, a hate or hurt illocutionary speech act at comment section of Atta Halilintar's YouTube is related to the criminal law. It is found assertive illocutionary speech act, expressive, directive, and commissive. From the data founded, it could be known that the most dominant of this speech act is assertive illocutionary speech act. It found five assertive illocutionary speech act, two expressive illocutionary speech act, one directive illocutionary speech act, and one commissive illocutionary speech act. They are implicit. It contains hate and insult to Atta Halilintar and his family. There are many factors for the presence of hate speech act posted on comment section. They are about netizen who dislike Atta Halilintar and his family, in order that they show their existence so that everyone could know them on social media. Therefore, the society forget about the attitude or social norms in the society. It includes how to use a good language, in order that there will not be people who hurt, especially about people's privacy. It is about UU ITE law Pasal 27 Ayat 3 UU ITE; states that it prohibits anyone from intentionally and without rights distributing and or transmitting and, or making accessible Electronic Information and, or Electronic Documents containing insults and or defamation. So that, we have to have a good attitude, especially in speech act in social media, when we want to post some written speech.

Conflicts of interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Citation: Nuril Laili Alfiani and Tadkiroatun Musfiroh. 2023. Illocutionary Hate Speech Act at Comment Section of YouTube Account Atta Halilintar (Analysis of Forensic Linguistics). *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*, 7(3): 6-14.

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